

A Comparative Study on Different Phenotypic Methods for Detection of Metallo Beta Lactamase Producing Bacteria in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Rural Medical College, LONI, (MS)

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Abstract:

Background: The emergence of metallo -beta - lactamase in NF-GNB is becoming a therapeutic challenge worldwide. Metallo beta lactamase producing bacteria are popularly known as superbugs due to their increased development of drug resistance to carbapenems. MBL producing bacteria mainly cause healthcare associated infections. Detection of MBL is also a challenge for routine microbiology laboratories. The aim of this study was to compare the different phenotypic methods for detecting MBL producing NF-GNB.

Methods: Total 307 clinical isolates of NF -GNB including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *pseudomonas* spp, *Acinetobacter boumannii*. These isolates were screened for imipenem resistance by Kirby Bauer disk diffusion methods and further tested for MBL detection by Disk-potential test, Double disk synergy test, Hodge test, Modified Hodge test, and E- Test.

Result and Analysis: Out of the 307 NF-GNB, 161 were found to be Imipenem resistant by Kirby -Bauer disk diffusion method and further imipenem resistant isolates tested for the MBL production which were 45 isolates are MBL producer. When these 45 isolates tested for MBL production by Hodge test 22(13.66%), by Modified test 31(19.25%), 34(21.11%) by Disk potentiation test, 41 (25.46%) by DDST and by MBL E test 45(27.95%) of the isolates were MBL producers.

Conclusion: The phenotypic methods are effective to detect MBL production in NF -GNB isolates. The sensitivity of MBL E -test (97.77%) was highest followed by DDST (91.11%) followed by DPT (75.55%) followed by MHT (68.88%) and lastly by Hodge test (48.88%). The E-test and DDST was very closely effective to detect MBL production.

Keywords: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, MBL, E-Test.

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Introduction

The introduction of carbapenem into clinical practice represented a great advance for treatment of beta -lactam resistant bacteria. Due to their broad spectrum of activity and stability to hydrolysis by most beta lactamases. The carbapenems have been the drug of choice for the treatment of infection caused by penicillin or cephalosporin resistant gram-negative bacteria.[1]

However, this scenario has changed with the emergence of carbapenem resistant strains especially in the non-fermenter gram negative bacilli (NF-GNB) such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter* spp.[2]

Metallo-beta-lactamases: (MBL) was first detected in 1960 in *Bacillus cereus* which was chromosomal in location. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* producing Metallo-beta lactamases was first reported from Japan which was plasmid mediated. Since early 1990's metallo-beta-lactamase encoding genes have been reported all over the world in clinically important pathogens such as *Pseudomonas* spp and *Acinetobacter* spp. MBL in gram negative bacilli is becoming a therapeutic challenge as these enzymes usually possess a broad hydrolysis by most beta lactam antibiotics including carbapenems. [3] MBLs belongs to the Ambler class B and have ability hydrolyze wide variety of beta lactam agents

such as penicillin's, cephalosporins and carbapenems but not monobactams. [4]

MBLs can be divided in to six categories according to their molecular structure namely IMP, VIM, GIM, SIM, and AIM. These enzymes require zinc for their catalytic activity and are inhibited by metal chelators such as EDTA and thiol-based compounds. [5] As a result of being difficult to detect such organisms due to their role in unnoticed spread within institutions and their ability to participate in horizontal MBL gene transfer with other pathogens in hospital in recent years, MBL gene have spread from non-fermenter to members of Enterobacteriaceae. [6][7] MBL-producing NF-GNB isolates have been responsible for serious infections, treatment failure and several nosocomial outbreaks in different parts of the world resulting in high morbidity and mortality, increased economic burden and a urgent need to establish a strong infection control protocol. [8]

Several phenotypic methods are available to detect MBLs. These tests include Disk-potential test using CAZ, ceftizoxime, cefepime, and cefotaxime.[9] (Arakawa Y, Shibata N, Shibayama K, Kurokawa H, Yagi T, Fujiwara H, et al. Convenient test for screening Metallo-Beta -Lactamases -producing gram negative bacteria by using thiol compounds. J. Clin Microbiol 2000; 38; 40-3) The modified Hodge test (MHT). [10,11] Double disk synergy test(DDST) using EDTA and IPM or CAZ. 10 Hodge test 10,11. Epsilon-meter-test (E-Test) a combined disk test (CDT) using EDTA with imipenem (IPM) or ceftazidime (CAZ).

The study was conducted to detect the prevalence of MBL in clinical strains of NF-GNB isolated at a tertiary care hospital in RMC, LONI (M.S.) and compare the sensitivity of different phenotypic test - disk potentiation test, double disk synergy test, Hodge test, modified Hodge test and E -test.

Materials and Methods

After the approval from Institutional Ethical committee, a study was carried out in Microbiology laboratory of a tertiary care hospital in Loni, (M.S.) to detect the production of Metallo-beta lactamase and compare the different phenotypic methods for detection of MBL in various clinical isolates

The study was conducted over a period of one year from July 2010 to July 2011 in the department of Microbiology, RMC, LONI, M.S., a tertiary care hospital. A total of 307 isolates of NF-GNB recovered from clinical specimens like pus, urine, blood, body fluids, sputum, conjunctival swab, vaginal swab, etc. were included in the study. The clinical isolates recovered from the both outdoor, indoor and ICUs patients irrespective of their age and gender, were identified bias per standard microbiological procedures.

Identification of Bacterial Isolates: All samples received in the Microbiology lab were cultured on Sheep blood agar, and in Mac Conkey agar media and incubated to 18 -24 hours at 37°C under aerobic condition and those showing typical colonies were further identified by gram staining and standard biochemical reactions.

Antimicrobial susceptibility was done on these strains by the Kirby -Bauer disk diffusion method as per the CLSI guidelines. All the disk was procured commercially (Hi-Media laboratory limited, Mumbai, India. The diameter of the zone of inhibition was measured and interpreted according to the CLSI guidelines.

Following antimicrobials disk were tested: Ceftazidime (30ug), ceftriaxone (30ug), cefepime (30ug), ceftizoxime (30ug), cefoxitin (30ug), imipenem (10ug), meropenem (10ug), piperacillin/tazobactam (100/10ug), ticarcillin/ clavulanic acid (75/10ug), aztreonam (30ug), gentamicin (10ug), amikacin (30ug), netilmicin (30 ug), ciprofloxacin (5ug), polymyxin B (300 units), colistin (10ug). In case of urinary isolates, ofloxacin (5ug) and norfloxacin (10ug) were also included. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 strains were used as the control strain.

Those strains found to be resistant were further tested for the MBL production by using different phenotypic methods viz disk potentiation test, DDST, Hodge test, modified Hodge test and E -test.

Methods for Detection of MBL Production

EDTA- disc potentiation test: A filter paper blank disk was placed and the following discs CAZ 30 ug, ceftizoxime 30 ug, cefotaxime 30ug, and cefepime 30ug, were placed 25 mm center to center from the blank disk on an MHA plate inoculated with the test organism. 10ul of 0.5 M EDTA solution was added to the blank disk, and the plate was incubated overnight in 35°C. Enhancement of the zone of inhibition in the area between the EDTA disk and any one of the four cephalosporin disks in comparison with the zone of inhibition on the far side of the drug was interpreted as a positive result.[10,12]

Imipenem-Edta Double -Disc Synergy Test: An IPM (10ug) disc was placed 20mm center to center from a blank disc containing 10 ul of 0.5 M EDTA (750ug) on an MHA plate inoculated with the test organism. After incubation at 37°C In 16 to 18 h, enhancement of the zone of inhibition in the area between IPM and the EDTA disc in comparison with the zone of inhibition on the far side of the drug (IPM was interpreted as a positive result.[10,12]

Modified-Hodge Test: Saline suspension ATCC 25922 *Escherichia coli* (matching 0.5 McFarland Turbidity Standard) was diluted 1:10 and the lawn

culture of the later were done on the MHA plate. The plate was allowed to stand for about 5 min at room temperature.

A 10 ug IPM disc was placed at the center, and the test organism was streaked in a straight line from the edge of the disc to the edge of the plate. The plate was incubated overnight at 35 °C in ambient air for 20 to 24 h. The presence of a distorted zone of inhibition or clover leaf type of indentation at the intersection of the test organism and E. coli, within the zone of inhibition of the IPM disc, was interpreted as a positive result. [10,12]

Hodge Test: In this test, lawn culture was done on a Muller Hinton Agar (MHA) plate with overnight broth culture of E. coli ATCC 25922; the opacity was adjusted to 0.5 McFarland's standard. Then, imipenem resistant test strain was inoculated by lawn culture on the same plate.

A 10 ug imipenem disc was placed in the center of the plate. 10 ul of 50 mM zinc sulfate solution was added on the imipenem disc and the plates were incubated at 37°C overnight. The presence of a distorted zone of inhibition was interpreted as a positive result for carbapenem hydrolysis screening by the Hodge test. [13,14]

Epsilometer Test (E-TEST): E-test MBL strips consist of a double-sided seven dilution range of imipenem IP (4-256ug /ml) and IP (1-64 ug /ml) overlaid with a constant 36 gradient EDTA. Individual colonies were picked from overnight agar plates and suspended in 0.855 saline to a turbidity of 0.5 Mc Farland's. A sterile cotton swab was dipped into the inoculum suspension, and a lawn culture of the inoculum was performed on an MHA plate. Excess moisture was allowed to be absorbed for approximately 15 minutes before the E-test MBL strip was applied. The plates were incubated for 16-18 h at 37 °C. The MIC endpoints were read where the inhibition ellipses intersected the strip. A reduction of imipenem MIC =3 two folding the presence of EDTA was interpreted, suggestive of MBL production. [15]

Results

A total of 1498 specimens processed from various samples such as blood, pus, urine etc. During a period of one year from July 2010 to July 2011. Out of which 320 NF-GNB were isolates and identified up to species level. Antibiotic sensitivity for each organism was done. Those organisms which were further tested for MBL production.

Table 1: Distribution of Non-fermentative gram-negative bacilli isolated from various clinical samples

Sample Type	Total Number	Percentage (%)
Blood	90	27.81
Pus	84	26.25
Urine	59	18.75
E.T. Tube	17	5.31
Sputum	16	5.00
Vaginal Swab	16	5.00
Pleural Fluid	12	3.75

Out of 320 NF-GNB 90 (27.81%) isolates were from blood, 84 (27.81%) from pus, 59(18.75%) from urine, 17(5.31%) from E.T. Tube, 16(5%) from sputum, 16(5%) from vaginal swab ,12(3.75%) from pleural fluid, 5(1.56%) from catheter tip, 4 (1.25%) from throat swab, 3 (0.93%) from ascitic fluid and 3 (0.93%) from stool .

Table 2: Distribution of the NF-GNB according to type of organisms (n=320)

Sample Type	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. species</i>	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	<i>A. baumannii</i>	<i>A. lwoffii</i>	<i>S. maltophilia</i>	<i>Alk. faecalis</i>	Nonfermented
Pus	45	19	8	10	1	-	-	1
Blood	71	5	-	13	1	-	-	-
Urine	33	7	-	14	2	-	-	2
C.S.F.	2	4	1	3	1	-	-	-
Sputum	10	2	1	2	1	1	-	-
Vaginal swab	14	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pleural Fluid	2	8	1	2	-	-	-	-
Endotracheal tube	7	6	-	2	1	-	-	-
Stool	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	-
Catheter tip	4	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Throat swab	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ascitic fluid	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-

Total	192 (60%)	58 (18.12%)	11 (3.43%)	46 (14.37%)	7 (2.18%)	1 (0.62%)	2 (0.62%)	3 (0.93%)
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Maximum number of isolates were *Aeruginosa* i.e., 192 (60%) followed by *Pseudomonas* spp. 58(18.12%), *A. baumannii* 46(14.37%) and *P. fluorescens* 11(3.43%).

Table 3: Imipenem resistant NF-GNB from the various samples

No fermenters	No and % of No fermenters	Total No and % of Imipenem Resistance
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	192 (60%)	86 (26.87%)
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	58 (18.12%)	39 (12.18%)
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	11 (2.5%)	8 (2.5%)
<i>A. baumannii</i>	46 (14.37%)	28 (8.75%)

Out of 320 NF-GNB, 26.87% *P. aeruginosa* were Imipenem resistant followed by 12.18% *Pseudomonas* spp. 8.75% *A. baumannii* and 2.5% *P. fluorescens*.

Table 4: Number and percent of Non-MBL and MBL producer organisms

Organisms	No and % of Non MBL Producer	No and % of MBL Producer
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	61 (70.93%)	25 (29.06%)
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	29 (74.35%)	10 (25.64%)
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	6 (75%)	2 (25%)
<i>A. baumannii</i>	20 (71.42%)	8 (28.57%)
Total	116 (36.25%)	45 (14.06%)

Maximum no of MBL producing organisms was *P. aeruginosa* (29.06%) followed by *A. baumannii* (28.57%), *P. spp* (25.64%) and *P. fluorescens* (25%).

Table 5: Comparison of Hodge Test, Modified Hodge Test, Disk-Potential Test, DDST AND MBL E-Test. MBL production (n = 161)

Organisms	HT	MHT	DPT	DDST	E.TEST
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	16 (18.60%)	19 (22.09%)	21 (24.41%)	23 (26.74%)	25 (29.06%)
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	4 (10.25%)	6 (15.38%)	7 (17.94%)	9 (23.07%)	10 (25.64%)
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	0 (0%)	1 (12.5%)	1 (12.5%)	2 (25%)	2 (25%)
<i>A. baumannii</i>	2 (7.14%)	5 (17.85%)	5 (17.85%)	7 (22%)	8 (28.57%)
Total	22 (13.66%)	31 (19.25%)	34 (21.11%)	41 (25.46%)	45 (27.95%)

E-test for MBL production showed maximum sensitivity for detection of MBL followed by DDST, DPT, MHT and HT.

Discussion

One of the major challenges in infection treatment is the emergence of metallo- β -lactamase-producing non-fermenting gram-negative bacilli, mainly from the healthcare setting. With this in view, this study was undertaken to ascertain the prevalence of MBL production among clinical isolates of NF-GNB and to comparatively assess different phenotypic methods for the detection of MBL in a setup of a tertiary care hospital [16].

Prevalence of MBL-Producing NF-GNB: This study involved 320 NF-GNB isolates, in which the most common organism was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, accounting for about 60%, followed by *Pseudomonas* spp. at 18.12%, *Acinetobacter baumannii* at 14.37%, and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* at 3.43%. The high prevalence of *P. aeruginosa* in this study is comparable to that of the previously reported high prevalence of this pathogen in nosocomial infections, particularly in ICUs, where most patients are immunocompromised or have invasive devices that increase the risk of infection [17]. Out of the total NF-GNB isolates, 161

(50.31%) were resistant to imipenem, a carbapenem antibiotic and a last resort for life-threatening bacterial infections. Maximum resistance was noted in *P. aeruginosa* 26.87%, followed by *Pseudomonas* spp. 12.18%, *A. baumannii* 8.75%, and *P. fluorescens* 2.5%. The very high level of imipenem resistance among these isolates is quite alarming, as it limits the treatment choices for these infections.

MBL Detection Methods: The production of MBL was detected in 45 (14.06 %) of the 320 isolates by various phenotypic methods. Amongst these isolates, *P. aeruginosa* showed the highest percentage of MBL production of 29.06%, followed by *A. baumannii* with 28.57%, *Pseudomonas* spp., with 25.64%, and *P. fluorescens* with 25%. This shows that *P. aeruginosa* and *A. baumannii* are major contributors to the spread of MBLs in healthcare settings and may present a serious therapeutic problem [18].

The sensitivities of the different phenotypic methods for MBL production detection varied significantly. Highest sensitivity was obtained for the MBL E-test, followed by DDST, DPT, MHT, and HT, at a rate of 27.95%, 25.46%, 21.11%, 19.25%, and 13.66%, respectively. The better performance of the MBL E-test and DDST can be attributed to their ability to effectively make a distinction between MBL-

producing and non-MBL-producing isolates. On the other hand, the findings indicate that HT and MHT are fewer sensitive techniques and may thus not be so reliable in detecting the presence of MBLs, especially in organisms that have a low level of production of these enzymes [19].

Implications and Recommendations: These findings underline the need for effective detection methods for MBLs in routine microbiological diagnostics. Because producers of MBLs are ubiquitous in NF-GNB, mainly represented by *P. aeruginosa* and *A. baumannii*, the enhancement of strict infection control policies and antibiotic stewardship programs may help prevent their dissemination in this setting.

That means that were it not for the sensitivities of the various phenotypic methods evaluated, it would be proper for laboratories to use several testing methods in order to detect these MBLs accurately. Specifically, MBL E-test and DDST have to be taken as primary methods in view of their high sensitivity and specificity. In addition, molecular methods would supplement phenotypic assays in giving a broad-based approach toward detection and characterization of isolates producing MBLs [20].

In summary, the increasing prevalence of MBL-producing NF-GNB has posed a significant challenge to the treatment of infections. Early and accurate detection of such organisms is quite important for guiding appropriate antibiotic therapy and in order to prevent further dissemination of resistance. This points out the requirement for persistent surveillance and effective methods of detection in health care settings in order to deal with the rapidly growing threat posed by MBL-producing bacteria.

Out of the phenotypic methods evaluated, the MBL E-test showed the best sensitivity, followed closely by the DDST. This mainly applies to the differentiation of the MBL-producing isolates from the non-MBL producers and is largely valuable for any clinical laboratory. Still, lower sensitivities obtained in the Hodge Test and the Modified Hodge Test may lead to underreporting of the MBL-producing strains if complete reliance is made on these tests.

The findings of this study thus underline the need for multiple phenotypic assays in detecting MBLs. Since phenotypic methods could still be limited, molecular techniques will further enhance the detection and characterization of organisms producing MBLs so that there could be a comprehensive approach to this public health threat.

Conclusion

The rising prevalence of MBL-producing NF-GNB has brought into sharp focus the imperative of augmenting infection control measures and

antibiotic stewardship programs without any further delay. These organisms, therefore, need to be identified early and accurately to lead to appropriate antimicrobial therapy and to avoid spread. Continuous surveillance with the execution of sensitive methods of detection in the healthcare setting must hence be ensured to lessen the effect of MBL-producing bacteria on the patient outcome and healthcare systems. The research also underlines that more studies are needed in collaboration to develop novel strategies to fight back antibiotic resistance and to safeguard public health.

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